

prof.dr. Rainer Funke

Emotions — the key to motivation in the experience society

Dr. Funke is professor for design theory in Potsdam. He is also head of the "Designinitiative Brandenburg-Berlin e.V.", institute for design development and promotion. From 1992 to 1996 he was founding dean of the school of design at the University of Applied Sciences in Potsdam. His main interest is the theory of design in semiotics and communication.

It must have been somewhere around thirty thousand years ago: it was the day of the winter solstice, dusk was falling, and, as the darkness closed in upon them, a group of adolescent males assembled on a rocky plateau in the vicinity of Lascaux in the south of what present-day maps call France. After having fasted for weeks, and with their state of awareness now altered by drugs, these young men, sworn members of a chosen élite, were experiencing a mixture of nervous anticipation and joyful resolve, for what was about to happen would be the most important event in their lives.

31

Before this night was out, they would make their encounter with the underworld and, in so doing, would not only cross the threshold from childhood into adulthood but, from this moment on, would belong to a select group of their tribe that was privy to the closely guarded secrets of their faith and of their tribal leadership.

And now the time is come: the procession of drummers and dancers approaches the group; the ground beneath their feet quivers. The elders stand around the initiates in a half-circle, and a high-ranking dignitary goes up to the adolescents. He bids them to follow him. After negotiating a short but circuitous path through the undergrowth, the group fetches up before a rugged wall of sandstone. The priest performs certain magic rituals and the rock face, affected by the magic, opens up. And through this aperture, which is just high enough to allow them to enter half-bent yet without crawling, the group disappears into the hill.

Inside, a small, well-tended fire is glowing, and beside it there are torches lying ready. Dancing and singing, the initiates set light to the torches. What now ensues is a procession, lasting several hours, through the cave's seemingly endless labyrinth of passageways, with the priest at its head and the young men following at due distance behind him.

And finally they reach their destination. It is a more spacious area, where the priest now guides each of the initiates to a specific place where he is to sit or lie. All of a sudden, supernatural figures emerge from the darkness: bisons, birds, symbols, human forms. They seem to be floating in space. This fascinating spectacle is accompanied by deafening noise, a spectacle that in reality is created by means of a carefully calculated interplay of alternating light and shadow in combination with the huge paintings on

the walls of the cave. Viewed from certain vantage points, and these are precisely where the initiates are now positioned, these forms seem three-dimensional, and the alteration in the lighting creates the illusion of movement.

And so, in this sanctum sanctorum, begins their awe-inspiring initiation.

Let us leave the ceremony at this point. It is possible, of course, that it was nothing like this at all.

The sensational discovery of the cave paintings at Lascaux has since given rise to a variety of theories. One such theory assumes that these depictions were used in combination with ritual ceremonies of a religious nature with the specific aim of internalizing at an emotional level both knowledge and patterns of behaviour, and that these depictions were created for this purpose. According to Howard Rheingold, referring to the palaeontologist John Pfeiffer (Rheingold, 1992), it essentially involved the creation of “subterranean cyberspaces ... with the aim of inculcating specific information into the memories of the first technologists” (p. 583). “They sought to put people into an altered state of consciousness in order lastingly to inculcate into their memories the growing corpus of knowledge” (p. 585). “What took place in the caves of Lascaux may well have been some of the earliest mnemonic ceremonies to make use of subterranean, three-dimensional art, myths and rituals, and possibly, too, of substances capable of altering a person’s state of awareness” (p. 587).

The visual characters here play a decisive role: they are an indispensable constituent element of the rituals guaranteeing memory and exclusivity. On closer consideration, this has less to do with art as, much rather, with precise functionalized commercial graphic art, graphic design or even virtual design. It could also be compared to scientific illustration. On the other hand, in view of the strict, ritualistic inclusion of visual communication with clear references existing between the forms of the objects and the forms of the ceremonies, it also has indeed a great deal to do with something like process design.

Has this, though, anything to do with design, as we understand it today, as industrial product- and communications-design?

Admittedly, in industrial society the practical and utilitarian functions of products and especially their operational functions are enmeshed in much more complex contexts. Even so, where there exist formalizations regulating the way people interact not only with one another but also with the things around

them, there are, I believe, parallels to be drawn with ancient societies. The communicative and aesthetic relationships that products convey essentially via design are indeed less compelling in the demands they make on people's behaviour than was the case in pre-industrial societies, for today there is, after all, a range of choices available. The variety of items put on the market by competing suppliers ensures this. Nevertheless, de facto, this freedom of choice only exists between several systems that are inherently stable, with each system necessarily determining those actions appropriate to it. We have learned to master a variety of languages at the same time, and to change from one to another at ever decreasing intervals. Yet as soon as we move about in one language, we are bound by its syntax.

Let us now compare the scene from the palaeolithic age described at the outset with the following event.

Peter has done enough work for one day. And as he mounts the stairs to his flat on the third floor, he is feeling vaguely weary, but this feeling is now overlaid with that thrill of anticipation which seizes him every time he changes, like today, for his evening out in the "Black" Club. He is soon out of his tie, shirt and trousers, and then quickly under the shower. That exquisite tingling which the small silver rings hanging from his pierced nipples and navel cause as he towels himself dry only serves to heighten this sense of anticipation. As he slips on his black leather gear, Peter takes a deep breath. One look in the mirror is proof enough: now he is a wholly different person. Liberated from his day-time jacket, the muscular physique of his chest is revealed, as is his rolling gait: like this, he is a real man.

The buckles on his boots chink as Peter, self-possessed and with a flourish, dillons through saloon-type doors and enters the "Black" Club. To his right, by the bar fashioned out of cold bare steel, and in front of the lattice bars that, prison-like, separate the lounge from the bar, Peter catches sight of his mates. At this very moment, though, Peter stops dead in his tracks: this morning he had inadvertently put on too much of his favourite perfume, a brand that is to be had in all the shops in town; now there is the danger that his friends might get wind of it. It is,

after all, one of the unwritten rules of this particular club that the men who frequent it, tough guys them all, naturally do not use any sweet-scented toilet water. Fortunately, though, the club is already pretty full, with the air blue enough to kipper the bronchials. No one is going to notice a thing. Peter goes up to his friends, greets them with a rough gesture and then seats himself, for the moment anyway, in front of a one-armed bandit. He looks cool, the way he sits there on the rough-hewn wooden stool, his left arm akimbo, casually working the

34 machine. Behind him the guys are circling the pool table. Beer is the drink here, downed from large pint glasses. The voices are loud, the music from the speakers, Heavy Metal.

Compared with the events at Lascaux, the element of rituality informing the course of events seems not dissimilar. And although we presume that the difference here lies primarily in the fact that the scene can be freely chosen, there is in this context, however, a further and important difference, a difference that is closely bound up with the effect design exerts in a mass-market society. Whilst Peter from the leather scene acts within a world where man's basic needs are assured, the people in Lascaux were permanently taken up with the necessities of survival (finding food, taking care of clothing and shelter, defending or extending their various territories, etc.). Under conditions of mass consumption, however, we live a new basic pattern in our relationship to the world. Schulze defines this pattern as "experience-orientation" (Schulze, 1995). The externally oriented motivation for action is increasingly being supplanted by an internally oriented motivation, one that is aimed at a particular experience with qualities that can be specifically planned, and which is becoming a determining feature of perception and action.

"With an externally oriented attitude to life, the goal of having children, for example, is regarded as having been attained when the children exist; with an internally oriented attitude to life, however, only when they make their parents happy ... Everyone can judge whether or not a car goes (externally anchored goal); but whether or not one gets a pleasant feeling when driving around in it (internally anchored goal), that is a question each person must decide for himself" (idem., p. 37).

In other words, when Peter does all manner of things to get himself ready for the leather scene, he does this in order to trigger off processes that take place inside of him as an emotionally specific experience. The adolescents in Lascaux, on the other hand, are ostensibly doing similar things, yet with a different goal, namely, of surviving in their tribe, fulfilling a duty, and this without questioning the value of the experience in the sense of its free availability. The value of the experience is firmly bound to the necessary situation. Even though the value of this experience is socially important for, and possibly partially aimed at, the imparting of knowledge and social classification, it is not the experience in itself that is the primary goal behind the participants' actions.

What was once a luxury available only to a small social upper-class has, in industrial society, become a principle of life shared by all. "Arrange your situation in the way you like it!" — the aim of having a pleasant life, i.e., of having pleasant experiences, has in large areas of everyday life replaced the aim of having a secure life, i.e., of surviving. The value of the experience is put above the utility value of the objects, of the services, and even of nature (nature is primarily perceived as leisure-time environment).

Design, in so far as it touches the surface of consumption, here also acts as a semiotic instrument in an experience-market that has emotions as its target, a market which, for its part, transforms with more or less consummate ease the demand for experiences into a demand for possession. Disappointed by the evening in the Club, Peter buys himself a new leather outfit. The criterion for success lies within the subject; success is dependent on reflection, on the active creation of the ability to experience, on the power to combine a succession of experiences with emotions, and possibly to establish stable patterns for doing this. Desire, the feeling of security, ecstasy, and so forth are qualities of experience that are anticipated in form-determined reflection, and which, as such, are contained within the contexts of forms, contexts that in the real world of images find their concretization also in design.

However, when it comes to gearing up the demand for experiences and all that the market has to offer in this regard, this seems to lead to problems of orientation. There is nothing any more that can be taken as a given; everything is regarded as formable. To quote Schulze on this: "The experience-market is only capable of producing ever more signs, an ever greater flood of material objects, sensory images and stimulating situations. The more this flood grows, the more difficult it becomes to maintain an overview of the situation, and the more blurred becomes the assignment of signs and significances. For this reason it is becoming harder to experience anything at all. Whilst the patterns of significance within us, which we seek to awaken through everyday aesthetic episodes, remain relatively stable over the long term because we cannot be constantly restructuring ourselves emotionally, the signs are fluctuating ever more frantically, so that it requires downright hard work both to practise and assimilate the

routines of experience and to build up firm links between signs and their significances" (idem. p. 116).

The objection that can be levelled against this view, however, is that it is precisely the work involved with such routines of experience that is performed with considerable gusto, and this to the extent to which the experience-orientation becomes the general scheme of assimilation, borne by the intersubjective analogy in the assignment of emotions to forms.

36

Peter has no difficulty integrating his working world and his leather-scene world with their different semi-otic continuities. The orientation succeeds, indeed it is the very effort put into this orientation, that is, into the overcoming of the specific uncertainties involved, which produces the pleasure.

The need for criteria of self-evaluation is covered by conventions, which for their part are reflected through the media (e.g., in design and advertising).

The pleasure taken in the utility value is conditioned by the pleasure taken in the experience value — with the concomitant danger of increasing disappointment.

In this respect, designers are experience-workers, as are architects, advertising experts, entertainers and journalists. In this process, design profits from the naïve assumption that it is sufficient to change the situation with material objects in the sense of experience-projections, to be present at certain events, or to choose particular personal relationships, without putting any effort of one's own into the subjective setting up of the experience. As life is regarded as being fundamentally safe and secure, it is now a matter of spending it with fun and happiness, a state of affairs which includes the unending and uncertain quest for orientation in the dynamically and conventionally fashioned forms of reflection.

Demand for experiences is rationalized and simultaneously rendered socio-dynamic by way of styles, by way of the formally determined norms of a particular social grouping, and such like. The fear of boredom and the fear of missing out on something become driving forces, for the more the experience becomes a goal in itself, the greater is the fear that the experience might not take place at all.

As a relative solution to this dilemma, we invent games (though, again, experience-oriented) that would seem to remove us from the cycle of experience-orientation as an end in itself by putting us into scenarios that once were threatening.

Peter in the leather-scene is at the moment in the midst of such a game. The signs of physical violence and the rule of power here serve to establish the link to an existence fictitiously under threat. Jeans as a sign of manual labour in an earlier age as well as the Marlboro Man are further examples of this type of game.

In this respect, design, even though it is directly concerned with material objects, invariably remains process design, too, because it is only real, that is, marketable, in its ability to conform to the conventional experience-processes aimed at describable communities of experience, with the essence of marketability consisting in the successful anticipation of the emotional

evaluation of material objects within the course of the respective experience.

What is true of human behaviour in general also applies to product-related actions: emotions constitute the central point for the motivation of actions.

The emotional demands made by the users upon, and the actual emotional reactions to, industrial products play a decisive role in the success or failure of these products both on the market and in their use. They transform objective expectations of a product into subjectively disposed expectations, and convert a decision to purchase into a personal act of purchasing. They transform information about what a product objectively offers in terms of its utility into what can be personally expected and experienced by way of utility, and, in relation to comparable situations, form stable patterns of expectation and experience. They put the user in the position of deciding subjectively which communication processes can be envisaged and realized with the help of such products, of deciding how far guide-models conducive to personal identification will be recognized, approved and accepted.

37

Emotions transform information about the surroundings into subjective relationships to the environment and thus set up a qualitatively perceptible and experienceable relationship to the world.

In addition to its suitability on a utilitarian, functional and operational level, the design of a product is the trigger for emotional reactions and projections. This is the case with all design objects, whether with investment items such as a production plant or a dentist's drill, with consumer goods such as a vacuum cleaner, an easy chair or a children's construction set, or with items of communication such as an airport information system, a theatre poster, an instruction manual, a web page, the through-designed furnishing of a company, a trade-fair stand or a special advertising campaign.

In contrast to the factual, utilitarian and operational reasons affecting design, the emotional reasons remain, in terms of their methodology, rather unclear. When, in the designing of a product, it involves ascertaining the nature of the object, its usability and suitability with regard to its application in particular processes, there are numerous reliable methods available for setting about this. It can be pretty clearly established whether, for example, a type-face is normally readable in specific contexts, or whether a lever can be depressed, and designers base their work on such requirements. But whether the packaging for a deodorant produces the feeling of the bodily freshness as imagined depends on such a wide variety of semiotic and communicative conditions that it proves difficult to devise any clear-cut plan, and any attempts at doing so are by and large rarely undertaken. It would seem that the uncertainty consumers have in deciding how best to escape boredom is matched on the other side by the uncertainty designers have in deciding what methods to apply in order efficiently to plan offers of emotions, i.e., experiences.

References

Howard Rheingold, *Virtuelle Welten. Reisen im Cyberspace* [Virtual Worlds. Journeys in Cyberspace], Hamburg, 1992

Gerhard Schulze: *Die Erlebnisgesellschaft* [The Experience Society], 5th impression, Frankfurt am Main, New York 1995

